

**LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF DEICTIC CENTER IN AGRICULTURAL TEXTS IN
UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES****Bozorova Munisa**

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Abstract. In this paper one the main phenomenon of pragmalinguistics the deixis and its role of creating deictic shift in agricultural texts in English and in Uzbek is discussed. The main features of deictic shift using deictic words are shown with the help of the scientific materials taken from scholarly articles and thesis. The pragmatic and cognitive analysis have been provided and the results have been given.

Key words: agricultural text, deixis, discourse, deictic center, spatial deixis, temporal deixis, discourse deixis.

INTRODUCTION

Pragmatics, which is one of the main fields of study in linguistics, is currently considered a very researched field, and the phenomenon of deixis, which is a part of pragmalinguistics, and its expressive features are studied in various texts and speech situations. Linguists study not only the phenomena existing in the literary language, however, the study of deixis in texts related to specific fields is also an actual issue. In particular, scientific texts related to agriculture are also distinguished by their unique style.[8] The word “deixis” is derived from Greek and means “to point, to indicate” [5]. Lyons and Stevenson have emphasized that deixis acts as a bridge between language and speech [4]. The expression of the phenomenon of pointing and the location of the deictic center in agricultural texts are also described in this article using examples.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Deictic means “sign” through language, and any linguistic form used to implement this “sign” is called a deictic expression [7]. Kravchenko said that “indication is a universal feature of the language system as a whole” [9]. In addition to the opinion of K. Buller, who cites the idea that indexical deixis is united around the origo, J. Lyons describes the phenomenon of deixis as egocentric and gives it as consisting of three parts: 1-the speaker, 2.The time understood from the speaker's speech; 3. Space in relation to the place where the speaker is speaking.[3] Linguist Yang Huang also added to this opinion, stating that “I-here-now” stands at the deictic center [2]. The linguist J. Rapaport, who worked on the field of deictic units in narrative structures, said that it is clear only if the reader is attentive to identify the deictic field and the person, time and place that is shown or indicated. Hamburg and Banfield expressed the opinion that the narrating author can create a deictic field even if he is not at the center of the story.[6] In this article, we used scientific articles and textbooks in English and Uzbek to determine the importance of deictic means in creating a field of display in scientific texts related to agriculture and its linguistic means. During the analysis, we used methods of classification, grouping, descriptive analysis, and comparison of examples.

RESULTS

Deictic means used in agricultural texts are among the means of creating a field of demonstration in agricultural texts. In agricultural texts, the person who speaks as the central speaker is often expressed as “we” (1) (2). If the transfer of the deictic center to another person is usually given by means of proper nouns, then leaving it in the center of the display field is performed by anaphoric display (3) (4). In the Uzbek language, the pronouns “bu”, “shu” perform the function of determining the space in the center of the indicator field (5), while in English, this function is expressed by the adverb “here” (7). However, in many cases, since the indication of the

primary time is carried out by the author, the adverbs “now” (8) and “hozir” (9) are used as a deictic tool in relation to the time indicated by the author. Another characteristic feature of agricultural texts is the expression of discursive deixis, in which the author changes the deictic center by directing the reader to the same part of the text. In this case, the demonstrative pronoun “these” and the phrase “quyidagi” serve as the establishers of the deictic center. In addition, by means of the pronouns “this” (10) and “bu”, “ushbu” found in the annotation parts of agricultural texts, the author uses the reader as an indicator reference to his scientific works.

DISCUSSION

It is necessary to take into account who wrote the original text to determine the display area in the text, WHEN—that is, to determine the time being marked throughout the text, and WHERE—to specify the space provided by the author. In order to determine the definition of the deictic center within the texts, Rapaport noted the need to pay attention to the following. 1) objects and events in the deictic center are relatively cognitively active (they can be named much easier than other objects in the text); 2) some aspects of the deictic center can be hidden within the text and they can be excluded as an exception, such as the phenomenon of ellipsis; 3) terms in the text and the possibility of their use are usually limited by the deictic center. Due to the fact that the author presents the sentences in the form of a compound sentence in agricultural texts, the establishment of a deictic center in it is often assigned to the main sentence. In agricultural texts, personal nouns or personal pronouns are often used to bring the person's deixis to the center of the display field to indicate WHO:

1) *To explore some of the tradeoffs that may be present under climate change we incorporate the profitability of changing the cropping system or adapting management to new climatic conditions (Climate smart agriculture p 182)*

2) *Biz qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion rivojlanishning asosiy ko'rsatkichi sifatida sohada intellektual mulk huquqlariga talabnomalar sonini va ITTKI ga xarajatlar tarkibi va hajmini tahlil qildik. (5-6-oktabr respublika konferensiyasi to'plami TDAU_SF 17)*

In the above examples, the task of defining the deictic center (1) (2) is given in English and Uzbek through the pronouns “we”- “biz” and in both examples, the author informs the reader that he is doing his scientific work. According to the style characteristic of scientific texts, there are cases where the author is not expressed in the form of “I”- “men” For this reason, giving the author with personal pronouns in the plural means not exclusivity, but an inclusive plural.

When establishing the deictic center in the display field using proper nouns, personal pronouns in an anaphoric state help to leave it in the deictic center:

3) *According to Docherty and Gliannini (2009), there is an urgent need to develop innovative approaches to address the climate change refugee problem. They call for a new legal instrument that will establish the human rights of climate refugees, mechanisms for humanitarian aid, and develop criteria to share the burden of relocating climate refugees, as well as financing the relocation efforts. (Climate smart agriculture p 61)*

4) *Orxideya suratlari va uning spirtlangan nusxasi Qirollik botanika bog'i ilmiy xodimi Yoxan Xermans tomonidan o'rganib chiqildi. U Cynorkis christae nomini olgan o'simlik ilm-fan uchun yangi ekanini tasdiqladi. (Agroilm 5(68) son 2020 46)*

In the given example in English, the person brought to the center of the deictic field is “Docherty and Giannini” as a proper noun, which is a means of ensuring its stay in the field of indication, and the pronoun “They” served as an indication of it. In the example given in the Uzbek language (4), the author used the proper name “Johan Hermans” to denote the person brought to the deictic center, and in subsequent places, it is held at the center of the field of indication by means of the personal pronoun “u”.

In literary texts, there are many means that serve to define space, among which place is expressed by adverbs of place, compound sentences with adverbial clauses. In agricultural texts,

nouns denoting place names and adverbs of place are used to bring space and WHERE to the center of the field:

5) *Shu sababli ham lalmi ekin yerlarining qaysi mintaqaga joylashganligiga va bu yerda qanday ekinlar yetishtirilishiga qarab eroziyaga qarshi tadbirlarni joriy etish yaxshi samara beradi. (Agroilm 5(68) son 2020 81)*

In the above example (5), the deictic center is designated by the phrase “lalmi ekin yerlar” while the phrase “bu yerda” is used to help it remain in the center.

6) *The terminology relating to genetic resources is in a state of flux. Here we use germplasm to denote the totality of genes and genetic combinations found in a species, oi a major portion of it. (Crop ecology 81)*

The English adverb of place “here” is distinguished by the fact that it refers to a specific place within the text, rather than a specific designated place. The author used the adverb “here” to draw the reader's attention to this space (6). In this case, a reference can be made to the same part of the text.

While verb tenses and adverbs of time are included among the means of indicating time in narrative texts and narrative processes, similar deictic signs can be used in scientific texts, particularly in agricultural texts:

7) *Legume-cereal rotations of the eighteenth century provide the model for these organic farming practices that are often now promoted without appreciation of their low productivity (Crop ecology 25)*

8) *Hozirda suv omborlaridan foydalanishdagi asosiy muammo – mazkur inshootlar yuqori b'eflari foydali sig'implarining loyqa cho'kindilar cho'kishi evaziga qisqarib borishidir. (Agroilm 5(68) son 2020 62)*

In the given examples, the expression of WHEN in the deictic center (7) (8) is performed by the adverbs “now” (17) and “hozirda” which refer everyone to this time in relation to the author's scientific activity, that is, in relation to the time he has set. In this regard, the real-time deictic representation “now-hozirda” differs from the representation within the text. In addition, the authors use the present tense form in general in the agricultural text, and in the analysis of literature, we can see more references to the past tense and time.

The most common situation in agricultural texts is discourse deixis, in which the author is distinguished by pointing the reader to a place within the text:

8) *The empirical case studies in these chapters cover lessons that have analyzed responses to climate change thus far and their implications for innovation, including technology adoption and adaptation, insurance schemes, and diversification of land and labor, and to a lesser extent internal migration. (Climate smart agriculture p53)*

9) *Quyida dehqonchilikda foydalaniladigan yerlar haqida qisqacha to'xtalib o'tamiz. (Z.Z.Abdushukurova O'zbekiston tuproqlarining agrokimyoviy tavsifi o'quv qo'llanma 40)*

In the given examples, the authors use the phrase “these chapters” (8) to provide information about the section they have provided and briefly indicate the information contained within it. In the following example (9), the author used the deictic phrase “quyida” to draw the reader's attention to the information that he is about to give, to establish the deictic center. In addition, in the annotation of the scientific work, the author uses words such as “mazkur” “ushbu” in the context of giving general information about his scientific work, and in English, the pronoun “this” is used as a discourse deixis:

10) *Ushbu maqolada dukkakli ekinlardan no'xat o'simligining bo'yining o'sishini ekish muddatlari va sxemasiga bog'liqligi bayon etilgan (5-6-oktabr respublika konferensiyasi to'plami TDAU_SF 353)*

11) *In this paper, we have comprehensively reviewed the sugarcane's phytochemical and microbial diversity. (Journal of agriculture and food research 12 2023 100549 9)*

In both examples (10) and (11), the author provides a brief overview of the research work performed and performs a deictic representation of the center of the representation field using the pronoun “this” (11) and the pronoun “ushbu”. Such cases in the composition of agricultural texts are found in the introductions of scientific articles, research papers, and textbooks.

CONCLUSION

Deictic means and the study of representation through them occupy an important place in pragmalinguistics, as well as in cognitive linguistics. Unlike fiction, the units belonging to the means that make up the deictic center are limited in scientific texts, in particular, in scientific texts on agriculture, this phenomenon is seen only from the author's point of view. Proper nouns and personal pronouns are used by the author to bring the person to the field of indication and leave him in the deictic center. We introduce more adverbs and demonstrative pronouns with means that keep space and time in the deictic center. Discourse deixis, which is considered the most productive in agricultural texts, not only attracts the reader's attention by providing a reference to the necessary parts of the text, and also acts as a reference to an entire scientific work in the annotation.

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